

ACTIVITIES OF RECREATION BASES CREATED IN THE PERIOD AFTER
INDEPENDENCE IN SURKHANDARYA REGION

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Annotation: This article discusses the issues of creating recreation areas in the Surkhandarya region in the period after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Recreation areas, Surkhandarya region, coast, reservoir, exploitation , " Uchkizil " , population, sand.

recreation areas were opened in the Surkhandarya region . One of them, the OXUS recreation area, which is located on the banks of the Uchkizil reservoir in the Termez region, was put into operation and began to provide services to the population.

On February 10-11, 2017, during a visit to the Surkhandarya region, the President got acquainted with the work carried out in the limited liability company "Pearl of Termez" and related to the construction of modern recreation and recreation facilities on the river bank of a reservoir in the heart of beautiful nature, as well as the creation of favorable conditions for local and foreign tourists.

Accordingly, the limited liability company " Termiz" Marvaridi " was reconstructed and new facilities were built. For recreation and restoration of the health of residents, a sanatorium was built with all amenities, equipped in a modern way. The Marvarid sanatorium was built next to it .

The vicinity of the Blue Reservoir is a territory with favorable conditions not only for the development of medical tourism, but also for the organization of eco and other tourist destinations. It is important that special attention is paid to these aspects of the region in the OXUS resort, which is being built by Universal Argalid LLC.

The businessmen claim that the place being built on five hectares of abandoned land will be a large complex with all modern amenities for local and foreign tourists. More than 17 billion soums will be spent on this .

Businessmen who turned this land into a prosperous corner and invited local and foreign tourists to the shore of calm waters leveled the sandy area here with the help of powerful equipment in two years, cleared it of stones and debris. Seedlings of landscape and fruit trees enriched the fields with fertile soil.

He planted and harvested over three thousand fruit trees and over a thousand seedlings of ornamental trees. At the initial stage, catering and trade points, a beauty salon, a swimming pool, and a playground were built and equipped. A mini-football field and a tennis court have been built. A zoo was opened in Moyazgin , various birds and camels were brought in. One 17-seater and 2 new three-seater motor boats were brought from abroad.

“The reservoir is a very convenient place for family vacations and recreation in the cool summer ,” says Umid Jalilov, manager of the recreation center. - The air will be cool and clean. Therefore, we try to create suitable conditions, based on the needs of domestic and foreign tourists.

To this end, we are laying the foundation for the construction of a hotel, a restaurant and three two-story cottages with an indoor pool. Next year we want to build ten more two-storey cozy cottages. All this will be equipped to the taste of tourists and quality service will be provided. Our zoo will be replenished with colorful animals. Those who come to our resort today also show that people's need for such places that are not inferior to foreign ones is increasing.

At the moment, about 50 new jobs have been created at the resort. When it is fully built and put into operation, more than 200 boys and girls will be employed on it.

- Of great importance in the further development of tourism is also the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 3, 2018 "On measures to improve the procedure for the development of ecotourism and water protection zones of reservoirs," says the deputy head. regional tourism development department of Surkhandarya region Zebuniso Alimardanova .

- Based on this, tourist facilities built on the banks of the reservoirs " Dzhanubiy Surkhan " in the Kumkurgan region, " Uchkizil " in the Termez region and " Topalang " in the Sariosi region, will become favorite places not only for local, but also for foreign tourists. This is a clear evidence of construction work being carried out along the Uchkizil reservoir . Next year, preparations are underway for the start of construction work in the area of the Topalang reservoir , adjacent to the charming mountains.

The resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated May 27 of this year "On additional measures for the effective use of the tourism potential of the Surkhandarya region and its development" defines the relevant tasks for establishing ecotourism in these regions.

The fact that the government pays attention to the development of industry in the region has created a favorable environment and an excellent opportunity for entrepreneurs to use water resources wisely. Limited Liability Company "Universal Argalid ", seeking to effectively use this facility, organizes interesting eco-tours for tourists, fishing for amateurs, boating, water sports, football, tennis, equestrian sports for riders, boat trips around the territory. new resort. The plans include the provision of services in such areas as

It is worth noting that such grandiose works are aimed at improving our national economy, providing employment for the population, providing them with decent rest, maintaining health, and ensuring a prosperous and prosperous life.

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